

Entrepreneurship as a ray of hope for Women

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Abstract:

Women entrepreneurs are those women who think of business enterprise, initiate it, organise and combine factors of production, operate the enterprise and undertake risks and handle economic uncertainty involved in running it. Women run successful enterprises, yet persistent gender inequalities continue to create major disparities in opportunities to start and grow a business. Entrepreneurship is a challenge and even more so if you're a woman. Despite their efforts and expertise, female entrepreneurs struggle a lot more than their male counterparts to make it big and get recognized within the business community. In general, their businesses tend to be smaller than those run by men, concentrated in sectors with limited potential for value addition and over-represented in the informal economy. The main challenges that women face in business are educational and work background, balancing their timeshare between work and family, problems of raising start-up capital, difficulty in - borrowing funds, problems of availing raw-materials access to the export market without intermediaries, as well as an overall psychological barrier on the part of banks, suppliers and clients alike, are a few of these challenges. In addition to this, a few of the challenges faced by rural women .

Key words: Women entrepreneurship , self help groups, central govt schemes, regulatory bodies , Sustainable development.

Women are an important human resource of the nation and every state should try to utilize them as mediators of economic growth and development. Encouragement for women's entrepreneurship is one of the ways for that. But unfortunately, it is seen that the traditional mindset of the society and negligence of the state and respective authorities are important obstacles to women's entrepreneurship development in India. There is a need for a continuous attempt to inspire, encourage, motivate and cooperate with women entrepreneurs, awareness

programs should be conducted on a mass scale with the intention of creating awareness among women about the various areas to conduct business. Women entrepreneurs play a vital role in economic development. Energetic entrepreneurship will be key to India's economic growth.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY :

- To identify success factors that contribute towards the development of women entrepreneurs.
- To identify the opportunities and challenges to face the competition in the market.
- To create awareness program on the problems and risk factors towards the financial inclusions for the women entrepreneurs.
- To develop and conduct more programs from the financial institutions for schemes related to women enterprises

Introduction:

History perspective /Background:

Women empowerment in ancient India transports to a terrain of mixed values and views . Women empowerment in India gathered much momentum after January 26 1950 following adoption of the constitution of India that carries rural clauses and sections that eliminate ambiguity over status of women. .

Thinking AHEAD ----- Connecting skill to industry: In the year 2018 ministry of MSME launched Udyam sakhi a network for nurturing social entrepreneurship creating business models revolving around with low cost products and services to resolve social equities .

Transforming Home maker to Entrepreneurship:

Empowering Women Entrepreneurs through MSME Schemes

The Indian economy has undergone a significant transformation in recent years, and women entrepreneurs have played a crucial role in this growth. With the rise of women-led businesses, the Government of India has taken several initiatives to empower women entrepreneurs and promote their businesses. The Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSME) sector has been at the forefront of these initiatives. Through various schemes and policies, MSME is empowering women entrepreneurs by providing them with financial and technical assistance.

Since the inception of the MSME schemes in 2019, around 1.38 lakh women entrepreneurs have started their businesses, accounting for approximately 30% of projects set up under the Prime Minister's Employment Generation Programme (PMEGP). This shows the impact that

MSME schemes have had in empowering women entrepreneurs in India. Moreover, the government has introduced special categories for women entrepreneurs, providing 25% and 35% subsidies for rural and urban areas, respectively.

Apart from these subsidies, the government has launched various loan schemes to provide financial assistance to women entrepreneurs. One such scheme is the Mudra Loan for Women, which provides loans ranging from Rs. 50,000 to Rs. 10 lakh to women entrepreneurs. Other schemes like Annapurna Scheme, Stree Shakti Yojana, Dena Shakti Scheme, Bhartiya Mahila Bank Business Loan, Mahila Udyam Nidhi Yojana, Orient Manila Vikas Yojana Scheme, Cent Kalyani Scheme, Udyogini Scheme, and Synd Mahila Shakthi Scheme provide financial assistance to women entrepreneurs for starting and expanding their businesses. The success of women entrepreneurs in India can be attributed to several factors. First and foremost, recognition and admiration play a significant role in motivating women to take up entrepreneurship. Women entrepreneurs are not only admired but are also respected for their contribution to society. Secondly, the prospect of creating employment and generating profit motivates women to take up entrepreneurship. By doing so, women can contribute to the economic development of the country and improve the quality of life. However, despite the various schemes launched by the government, women entrepreneurs still face several challenges. One of the primary challenges is the lack of good quality infrastructure in rural areas. Sound financial services and management and technical assistance are also essential for women entrepreneurs to succeed. Additionally, there is a need to increase awareness among women in rural areas about the various schemes and policies available to them. Vocational training programs and removing sociolect-cultural barriers can also go a long way in promoting women entrepreneurship in India.

1. **Lack of education:**

The lack of education among rural women in India is a major hindrance to their entrepreneurial success. Many women entrepreneurs are unable to keep up with the latest trends and advancements in their industry due to the lack of access to quality education. This, in turn, limits their ability to innovate and remain competitive in the market. Moreover, without proper education, women entrepreneurs may also lack knowledge on how to access and utilize government schemes and support. This can result in missed opportunities and potential benefits for their businesses. To address this issue, there is a need for the government and other stakeholders to focus on promoting and improving education for women in rural areas. This can be achieved through initiatives such as increasing the number of schools and colleges in rural areas, providing scholarships and incentives for women to pursue higher education, and offering training programs and workshops specifically for women entrepreneurs. In

addition, private organizations can also play a role by providing mentorship and networking opportunities to help women entrepreneurs gain knowledge and skills in their respective industries. With proper education and support, women entrepreneurs in rural areas can break barriers and achieve success in their businesses.

2. **Male-dominated society:** As far as rural areas are concerned, people have a set outlook that women are only for household work. Their entry to business requests the approval of head of the family. Entrepreneurship has traditionally been seen as male conserved and male conquered. Thus male entrepreneurs become obstacle in the success of women entrepreneurs.

According to the survey of Catalyst research 2021 -22

Male-Dominated Occupations Are Those Comprised of 25% or Fewer Women.

Male-dominated industries and occupations are particularly vulnerable to reinforcing harmful stereotypes and creating unfavorable environments that make it even more difficult for women to excel.

In the United States, only 6.5% of women worked full-time in male-dominated occupations in 2020.

However, the youngest Millennial in the US are less segregated by sex in occupations compared to previous generations.

Some job growth for women is driven by employment in male-dominated fields.

Between 2016 and 2018, women's employment increased by 5.0% in industries consisting of two-thirds men.

In Australia, women's employment in civil engineering and software programming has grown steadily over the past decade, outpacing men.

But challenges remain:

Despite growth in information and communications technology, since 2010 women's share of jobs in the sector in the European Union dropped to only 18% in 2019.

Emerging jobs in the Future of Work already show gender gaps globally, especially in growing fields like data and AI (32% women) or cloud computing (14% women) that require disruptive technical skills.

Women Face Challenges Working in Male-Dominated Workplace Cultures

Women working in male-dominated industries face a variety of challenges, including:

Societal expectations and beliefs about women's leadership abilities.

Pervasive stereotypes, such as that of the "caring mother" or office housekeeper.

Higher stress and anxiety compared to women working in other fields.

Lack of mentoring and career development opportunities.

Sexual harassment.

Unfortunately, reports of sexual harassment are more prevalent in male-dominated industries.

In a 2017 survey, 28% of women working in male-dominated industries stated they had personally experienced sexual harassment, compared to 20% of women in female-dominated industries.¹⁷

This heightened level of harassment is a problem even before women enter the workforce.

One study found that women pursuing male-dominated university majors experience higher levels of harassment than women earning degrees in gender-equivalent (no more than 60% of a single gender) majors.

3. **Social barriers:** Religions and castes dominate with one another and hamper women entrepreneurs. In rural areas, they face more social barriers as they are always seen with doubtful eyes.
4. **Tough competitions:** Generally women entrepreneurs do not utilize high technology in the process of production. In a market where the competition is too tough, they have to fight hard to stay alive in the market against the organized sector.
5. **High cost of production:** A number of factors including inefficient management contribute to the high cost of production which stands as an uncertain block before women entrepreneurs.
6. **Lack of motivation:** Motivation plays a vital role in running an enterprise. Women entrepreneurs because of their intrinsic nature, sometimes feel less confident which is essentially a motivating factor for themselves in the administration of an enterprise successfully.
7. **Legal formalities:** Various legal formalities is required for running an enterprise which becomes a commotion task on the part of women

entrepreneur because of the incidence of corrupt practices in government offices.

These challenges are compounded by women's care responsibilities, which create additional pressure on women entrepreneurs; time, workload and well-being, as well as by unfavourable institutional environments that can result in uneven access to land and decision-making roles, and inadequate social protection coverage.

The journey of women entrepreneurs is not easily many hurdles are still there which lurk women into taking the big leap. A pleasant atmosphere is needed for women to participate actively in entrepreneurial activities. There are a lot of agencies which come forward and take initiative in promoting women's entrepreneurship like government, non-government, promotional and regulatory agencies.

Main Issues:

Success stories of women Entrepreneurs:

In recent years the number women entrepreneurs has been on the rise and many have achieved remarkable success in their respective fields. Let us introduced a women entrepreneur who have started her business as proprietor-ix in trendy jute(Making of jute bags) Established in the year 2016 at Hyderabad ,Pragati Nagar ,Telangana.

Trendy jute are engaged with manufacturing, whole sale and trader of backpack bag, etc. This company ensures that these products are timely delivered to our clients and reached the target nearly 30 lacks with the initial investment of 4 lakh. Nearly 15 employees are working under her and providing more employment opportunities for skilled and UN skilled people.
Fig.1

About Rural Technology Park at Hyderabad, Telangana
2. Clay jewellery

Fig

Fig 3. Ayurveda Products

Fig 4. Ayurveda

products

Fig 5. Handicrafts.

NIRD (National Institute of Rural Development) is a well-known institution in Telangana, which provides an excellent platform for women entrepreneurs to continue their businesses. The institution has provided workspace to several women entrepreneurs free of cost to carry out their business activities. The products created by these entrepreneurs are then sold to the general public. Some of the products sold include honey, jewellery, cosmetics, handicrafts, mushrooms, textiles, pottery, Ayurveda medicine, manufacturing of lightweight bricks for construction, handicrafts, paper plates made using leaves, and sanitary napkins. The platform provided by NIRD has helped these women entrepreneurs to continue their businesses without worrying about the cost of workspace. Moreover, it has provided them with an opportunity to showcase their products to a wider audience, which has helped them to generate more revenue. Apart from this, the institution also provides a platform for women to work under employers, organize exhibitions and stalls, and carry out online marketing for social media groups.

The success of these women entrepreneurs has motivated other women to take up entrepreneurship. In this sense, organizations like ALEAP and WE HUB have been conducting more programs with effective collaboration with MSME, T HUB, and Telangana government. These programs have helped women to learn more about entrepreneurship and the resources available to them. The collaboration with government organizations has helped to create a supportive environment for women entrepreneurs, which has encouraged them to continue their businesses.

The success of NIRD has demonstrated the importance of providing women entrepreneurs with an enabling environment to carry out their businesses. The institution has provided women entrepreneurs with the necessary resources and support to continue their businesses. The support provided by NIRD has

helped these women entrepreneurs to create their own identity, become financially independent, and contribute to the economy. Moreover, the success of women entrepreneurs in Telangana has shown that women can succeed in any sector they choose. Women entrepreneurs today have successfully tapped into lesser-explored sectors from food, beauty, travel, sanitation, IT, automobile, and even innovation. To make things easier, the Govt of India has stepped up by introducing loan schemes for women. These women entrepreneur schemes have been quite helpful in getting the financial assistance required for their entrepreneurial journey. In conclusion, NIRD has provided an excellent platform for women entrepreneurs in Telangana to continue their businesses. The institution has provided women entrepreneurs with workspace, resources, and support to carry out their activities free of cost. The success of NIRD has motivated other organizations to collaborate with the government to create an enabling environment for women entrepreneurs. This has encouraged more women to take up entrepreneurship and contribute to the economy. With the right support and resources, women entrepreneurs can create positive outcomes not only for themselves but for their communities and the economy at large.

In conclusion, the state of Telangana has emerged as a land of opportunities for women entrepreneurs. Women entrepreneurs are driving innovation, creating job opportunities, contributing to economic growth, and promoting diversity and inclusion in the business world. The government of Telangana has taken various initiatives to support and promote women entrepreneurship through schemes like ALEAP and WE HUB. These programs have provided financial assistance, skill development, infrastructure, and networking opportunities to women entrepreneurs.

Furthermore, institutions like NIRD have provided workspace and opportunities for women entrepreneurs to showcase their products and market them to the general public. The success stories of women entrepreneurs in Telangana prove that they have the potential to make a positive impact on their communities and the economy at large.

However, there is still scope for improvement. Proper implementation and execution of government schemes is crucial to achieving the intended results. Furthermore, awareness and vocational training programs need to be increased in rural areas to encourage women to take up entrepreneurship. Improved access to good quality infrastructure, sound financial services, management and technical assistance, and the removal of socio-cultural barriers are also important to promote women entrepreneurship in Telangana.

In conclusion, Telangana has immense potential for women entrepreneurship, and with the right support, more and more women entrepreneurs can emerge and contribute to the development of their communities and the economy.

The case study is for the women entrepreneurs who are residing in the society by doing their small business with least budget investment to start their life based on their standards. There are so many stories which inspires them a lot by tackling their situation . I have seen so many stories of women entrepreneurs who have start up their Eco friendly products that designs and creative to make the products like jute bags , paper bags ,sanitary napkins and handicrafts made by banana fibre and also chocolates making concepts. In Telangana we have a Rural Technology park which is a part of Telangana government and initiates the business opportunities among the rural women and also SERP is the organization which studies about the poverty elimination in the rural areas and also economic empowerment of women through entrepreneurship.In conclusion, MSME schemes have played a significant role in empowering women entrepreneurs in India. These schemes provide financial and technical assistance to women entrepreneurs, helping them to start and expand their businesses. The success of women entrepreneurs can be attributed to several factors, including recognition, profit generation, employment generation, economic development, and improved quality of life. However, there is a need to address the challenges faced by women entrepreneurs, such as the lack of good quality infrastructure, sound financial services, and management and technical assistance. By doing so, India can further promote women entrepreneurship and harness the full potential of women-led businesses.

Fig 6:

Score

Histogram of Score

Outcome:

Successful women entrepreneurs have the potential to create positive outcomes not only for themselves, but for their communities and the economy at large. Here are some of the outcomes of successful women entrepreneurs.

1. Job creation: Successful women entrepreneurs create job opportunities for others, which helps to boost economic growth and reduce unemployment rates. This is particularly important in countries where job opportunities may be limited. And women may face discrimination in the workforce.
2. Incubation: Women entrepreneurs bring new ideas, products, and services to the market, which can lead to greater innovation and competition. This can drive economic growth and help to solve social and environmental problems.

3. Empowerment: Successful women entrepreneurs inspire and empower other women to pursue their entrepreneurial dreams. They serve as role models and show that it is possible for women to achieve success in the business world, which can help to break down gender stereotypes and promote gender equality.
4. Philanthropy: Many successful women entrepreneurs are also philanthropists and use their success to give back to their communities. They may support social causes, fund reserved and development, or provide resources to underprivileged groups.
5. Economic growth: Women entrepreneurs contribute to the overall economic growth of their countries by starting business, creating job and generating revenue. This can help to boost GDP and improve the standard of living for people in their communities.
6. Diversity and inclusion: Successful women entrepreneurs bring diversity and inclusive to the business world. They may have difference perspectives and approaches to business words. They may have difference perspectives and approaches to business, which can lead to more diverse and inclusive workplaces and help to break down barriers and promote equality.

Conflicts:

Fewer sectors are Women friendly, Lack of Social and Institutional Support, Poor Funding Prospects, Lack of Access to Professional Networks, Pressure to Stick to Traditional Gender Roles, Lack of an Entrepreneurial Environment, Limited Mobility, and Lack of Education.

In today's world, women are breaking barriers and making strides in various fields, including entrepreneurship. Successful women entrepreneurs have the potential to create a positive impact not only for themselves but also for their communities and the economy at large. By empowering women entrepreneurs, there can be 360-degree development worldwide, leading to more significant changes in parameters such as job creation, innovation and creativity, empowerment, philanthropy, economic growth, diversity, and inclusion. One of the significant impacts of successful women entrepreneurs is job creation. By starting and growing businesses, women entrepreneurs are providing job opportunities to people in their communities. In many cases, these jobs can be of high quality, providing employees with good salaries, benefits, and career development opportunities. This can help to boost the overall economy, as more people have disposable income to spend, leading to increased demand for goods and services.

Women entrepreneurs also drive innovation and creativity, which can lead to the development of new products and services that address societal needs. By being able to think outside the box, women entrepreneurs can bring fresh ideas to the table, which can help to address some of the challenges that society faces. This can help to improve people's lives, create new markets, and spur further economic growth. Empowerment is another important outcome of successful women entrepreneurs. By starting and running their businesses, women can gain

the confidence and skills necessary to take on leadership roles in their communities and beyond. This can help to break down gender barriers, as women are increasingly seen as capable of taking on positions of power and influence. Additionally, successful women entrepreneurs can serve as role models for other women, inspiring them to pursue their entrepreneurial dreams and break through barriers of their own.

Successful women entrepreneurs are also known for giving back to their communities. Many women entrepreneurs use their businesses as a means to support causes that they care about, such as social and environmental issues. This philanthropic spirit can help to improve the overall quality of life in their communities, creating a more vibrant and healthy society.

In addition to the positive impact on their communities, successful women entrepreneurs can also contribute to economic growth. By starting and growing their businesses, women entrepreneurs can increase the GDP of their regions, leading to greater economic prosperity. This can create a virtuous cycle, as increased economic activity can lead to more opportunities for job creation and innovation.

Finally, successful women entrepreneurs can promote diversity and inclusion in the business world. By breaking down gender barriers and promoting equality, women entrepreneurs can help to create a more inclusive and diverse business ecosystem. This can help to foster innovation, as a greater diversity of ideas and perspectives can lead to better problem-solving and decision-making.

In conclusion, the positive outcomes of supporting and promoting women entrepreneurs and their businesses are clear. Successful women entrepreneurs can create jobs, drive innovation, empower others, give back to their communities, contribute to economic growth, and promote diversity and inclusion in the business world. By providing targeted support to women entrepreneurs, such as access to funding, mentorship, and training programs, we can help to foster the growth of women-led businesses and promote overall economic prosperity. As we continue to break down gender barriers and promote equality, we can create a more inclusive and diverse business ecosystem that benefits everyone.

Fig 7

16-17/28

Referances:

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